

Spatial Relationship Criterion #6: Polylines Intersect Polylines

'Polylines Intersect Polylines' refers to a spatial relationship criterion where two or more polyline features from one layer, intersect two or more polyline features from another layer in a GIS environment. This criterion is used to identify places where different linear features, such as roads, pipelines, or utility lines, physically cross or share common points.

In GIS analysis, this helps ensure that certain connectivity, overlap, or crossing relationships are correctly represented between layers, aiding in tasks like network analysis, infrastructure management, and spatial data validation.

Our practical example involves working with a Detailed Urban Plan in a digital CAD format. This plan consists of multiple layers, including building lines, land parcels, existing streets, buildings, stormwater drainage, water supply systems, and more. Among these layers are underground power cables and underground telecommunication lines—both optical and copper. The telecommunication lines are categorized as either existing or planned.

In this example, we'll focus on determining if, and where, the planned telecommunication optical cable trench intersects with the existing underground electrical power cables. These power cables are buried for electricity transmission and distribution, making this analysis crucial. It's a high-risk task, as digging and trenching without proper knowledge of existing cables can be hazardous for field workers.

Our second analysis will focus on identifying which land parcels the existing new optical cable crosses. This is important for future assessments related to land ownership and legal rights.

Let's dive in. SGIS integrates these capabilities into both SGIS Desktop and SGIS v.R software.

Fig. 1 Demonstrating a Detailed Urban Plan in digital CAD format, showcasing multiple layers such as building lines, land parcels, existing streets, buildings, stormwater drainage, and water supply systems.

Let's begin by accessing the 'Select by Layer' function. You can find it on the main toolbar of the user interface—just click to open it.

Fig. 2 Accessing the 'Select by Layer' function from the main toolbar on the user interface.

Fig. 3 Displaying the dialog window after activating the 'Select by Layer' function, with the dropdown list showing the selection of the 'Polygons Intersect Polygons' spatial relationship criterion.

After activating the function, a dialog window will appear. From there, we simply open the dropdown list and choose the 'Polygons Intersect Polygons' spatial relationship criterion.

From the second dropdown list, we'll choose the planned telecommunications optical cable trench layer, as that's the focus of our spatial selection.

Then, from the third dropdown list, we'll select the layer representing the underground electrical cables. Finally, we click 'Select' to execute the selection.

Fig.4 Selecting the planned telecommunications optical cable trench from the second dropdown list and the underground electrical cable layer from the third dropdown list.

As we can see, two optical cable trenches are highlighted on the graphics panel. The default highlight color is red, but as mentioned before, this can be customized. In this example, with so many layers, the selected lines may not stand out clearly.

Fig. 5 Two optical cable trenches are highlighted in red on the graphics panel. Though the red highlight color can be customized, the selected lines may be hard to spot among the many layers. They are clearly listed in the 'Selected Elements' panel on the right side of the interface for easy reference.

However, they are listed in the 'Selected Elements' panel on the right side of the interface.

To make it easier to work with the layers, we'll export the selection as a separate layer using the 'Selected Elements in New Layer' function. This will allow us to disable all other layers, making the selected elements much clearer in the graphic panel.

Fig. 6 Exporting the selected optical cable trenches as a separate layer using the 'Selected Elements in New Layer' function, allowing us to simplify the display by disabling all other layers for clearer visualization in the graphic panel.

Fig.7 Selecting land parcels using the 'Select by Layer' function with the PolyLines intersect PolyLines mode. The Land Parcels layer is chosen as the layer to be selected, while the condition layer is set to the existing telecommunications cable trench.

Once we've completed the previous step, we can head back to the 'Select by Layer' function to repeat the process with different layers. This time, we want to identify and isolate the land parcels that the existing telecommunications cable trench crosses. These parcels are crucial for further analysis regarding land ownership and legal rights.

We'll use the same selection mode—'Polylines intersect Polylines'—since this is a CAD file, and the land parcels are represented as polylines rather than polygons. For the 'Layer to be selected', we'll choose 'Land Parcels', and the condition layer will be the existing telecommunications cable trench. Now, we simply click on 'Select'.

Fig.8 The land parcels are selected and highlighted on the graphics panel.

Fig.9 The parcels are separated into their own layer for better organization and further management.

The land parcels that meet our criteria are quickly selected and highlighted on the graphics panel. They're also listed in the Selected Elements tree for easier management. Next, we'll separate them into their own layer for better organization.

Next, we'll disable all the layers in the Layers panel and only open the ones necessary for our analysis. This includes the land parcels, the planned and existing telecommunications cable trench, the underground electric power cable layer, and a layer for additional elements like pavements and similar polylines. We will also include the two separate layers created from our previous selections: the layer where the planned trench intersects with the electric cable and the parcels that the new telecommunications cable passes through.

Fig.10 The Layers panel is streamlined to show only the essential layers for our analysis, including land parcels, telecommunications trench, underground electric cable, and additional elements. This clearer workflow enhances processing efficiency. The interface resembles a CAD environment while functioning within a GIS framework, enabling users to input attributes into each layer.

By narrowing down the layers, our workflow becomes clearer for further processing. As shown in Fig.10, the interface resembles a CAD environment, even though it operates within a GIS framework, allowing users to input attributes into each layer.

We've included Fig.11 and Fig.12 to enhance visual clarity.

In Fig.11, the existing telecommunications trenchline is prominently displayed in a fuchsia color, with the separated land parcel polylines overlaid in a dashed red.

Fig.12 showcases the planned telecommunications cable trench in a bold yellow line, while the electrical cable network is represented by a thin sepia-colored polyline.

With this, we have completed the procedure.

Fig.11 The existing telecommunications trenchline is shown in fuchsia, clearly highlighting its position, while the separated land parcel polylines are overlaid in a dashed red for easy identification.

Fig.12 The planned telecommunications cable trench is illustrated with a bold yellow line, contrasting with the electrical cable network depicted as a thin sepia-colored polyline.